

KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE OF BREAST CANCER SELF EXAMINATION AMONG FEMALE STUDENTS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA.

F.M. Onyije,¹ V.C. Zenebo² and Y.I. Oboma³

¹Department of Human Anatomy, ³Department of Anatomical Pathology, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria, ²Department of Histopathology, Medical Laboratory Services, Braithwaith Memorial Specialist Hospital, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Breast cancer is one of the most common cancers among females worldwide. A cross-sectional survey was conducted in Bayelsa and Rivers State between March and August 2010 to assess knowledge, attitude and practice of breast cancer self examination among female students in tertiary institutions. There was a poor knowledge on the etiology of breast cancer as Only 207 (39%) were aware that breast cancer can be inherited. 195 (37%) of the female students believe that breast cancer can be caused by evil spirit, while 129 (27%) had no idea if it was caused by evil spirit or not. Respondents had a very good knowledge of the signs and symptoms of breast cancer as 372 (72%) agreed that breast cancer usually present as a painless breast lump, 84 (16%) Disagreed while 57 (12%) were not aware of its signs and symptoms. Two hundred and thirteen (37%) of the respondents claimed to have heard about breast cancer self examination through a doctor, 153 (27%) from publications, 70 (12%) acknowledged Television, 18(3%) claimed their source was from churches/religious groups, while 33 (6%) of the respondents got their information from women organizations and 84(15%) from Nigerian cancer society programs. There was good of knowledge of breast cancer by the respondent but the practice of breast cancer self examination was below average which suggest that irrespective of the knowledge acquired, the practice of breast cancer self examination was still poor among female students in tertiary institutions.

KEYWORDS: Breast cancer, Symptoms, Questionnaire, Women, Bayelsa and Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is one of the most common cancers among females worldwide. There is increasing evidence that breast and other cancers originate from and are maintained by a small fraction of stem/progenitor cells with self-renewal properties. Whether such cancer stem/progenitor cells originate from normal stem cells based on initiation of a de novo stem cell program, by reprogramming of a more differentiated cell type by oncogenic insults or both remains unresolved (Xiangshan *et al.*, 2010). Global statistics show the annual incidence of breast cancer is increasing and this is occurring more rapidly in countries with a low incidence rate of breast cancer (Parkin *et al.*, 2005; Wilson *et al.*, 2004), from 1975–1990, Asia and Africa have experienced a more rapid rise in the annual incidence rates of breast cancer than North America and Europe (Sasco. 2001). In African breast cancer patients tend to present at a young age, with large tumors and multiple nodal involvements, and have poorer clinical and pathological prognostic factors compared with Caucasian patients. These characteristics are somewhat similar to that of African-Americans but are in contrast with those of non-Hispanic Whites in the USA, thus heightening the interest in the role of genetic factors in the etiology of breast cancer in general, and in people of African origin in particular (Adebamowo and Ajayi 2000; Rose and Royak-Schaler 2001)

Recent observations show that the frequency of breast cancer has risen over that of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas and cervical cancer in Nigeria (Thomas 2000). This trend could be attributed to several factors such as lack of knowledge about breast cancer and the usefulness of breast self-examination.

In 2008, an estimated 182 460 cases of invasive and 67 770 cases of noninvasive breast cancer were diagnosed, and 40 480 women died of breast cancer. Incidence increases with age, and the probability of a woman developing breast cancer is 1 in 69 in her 40s, 1 in 38 in her 50s, and 1 in 27 in her 60s (Heidi *et al.*, 2009)

One of the most important risk factors for breast cancer is the occurrence of breast or ovarian cancer among family members. Women with one or more first-degree relatives with breast cancer have a 1.8-3.0-fold increased risk of

developing the disease (Makarian *et al.*, 2007). The prevalence of women with a family history of breast cancer has been estimated to range from 5 to 19% (Murff *et al.*, 2005).

The relative frequencies of breast cancer among other female cancers, from Cancer Registries in Nigeria were 35.3% in Ibadan, 28.2% in Ife-Ijesha, 44.5% in Enugu, 17% in Eruwa, 37.5% in Lagos, 20.5% in Zaria and 29.8% in Calabar (Banjo 2004). In all the centers, except Calabar and Eruwa, breast cancer rated first among other cancers. Further reports showed that majority of cases occurred in pre menopausal women, and the mean age of occurrence ranged between 43–50 years across the regions. The youngest age recorded was 16 years, from Lagos (Banjo 2004).

There is strong evidence suggesting that older women in the developed countries are more likely to delay their presentation with breast cancer, (Ramirez *et al.*, 1999), there is data suggesting that factors related to women's knowledge and beliefs about breast cancer and its management may contribute significantly to medical help-seeking behaviors (Ferro *et al.*, 1992; Maxwell *et al.*, 2001).

The prevalence of breast cancer in recent years has prompted women to seek medical advice randomly with minimal breast symptoms, but only a small number of women are aware of this in the society, with childbearing extending practically over the entire reproductive period of life. Due to the conservative nature of the society, many females will refrain from seeking medical advice out of shyness until their disease becomes far advanced, particularly in cases of carcinoma of the breast. Often Breast cancer engenders an exceptional level of fear among women, most probably because of its external location on the body, with all of the obvious cosmetic and psychosocial implications, coupled with proper methods of conducting breast self examination (BSE) or are aware of the importance of radiological screening for breast cancer (Alam *et al.*, 2006).

The three screening methods recommended for breast cancer includes breast self-examination (BSE), clinical breast examination (CBE), and mammography. Unlike CBE and mammography, which require hospital visit and specialized equipments and expertise, BSE is inexpensive and is carried out by women themselves. Several studies, based on breast cancer patient's retrospective self-report on their practices of the exam, have established that a positive association exists between performance of the exam and early detection of breast cancer (Philip *et al.*, 1986).

Breast cancer presents most commonly as a painless breast lump and a smaller proportion with non-lump symptoms. For women to present early to hospital they need to be "breast aware"; they must be able to recognize symptoms of breast cancer through routine practice of practicable screening. At the present time, routine mammography cannot be recommended in developing countries due to financial constraints and the lack of accurate data on the burden of breast cancer in these countries (Okobia *et al.*, 2006). There is also evidence that most of the early breast tumors are self-discovered (Smith *et al* 1980) and that the majority of early self-discoveries are by BSE performers (Smith *et al* 1980). Despite the advent of modern screening methods, more than 90% of cases of cancers of the breast are detected by women themselves, stressing the importance of breast self – examination (Parkin *et al.*, 1992). The purpose of a BSE is to learn the topography of the breasts; which in turn will allow for one to notice changes in the future in order to detect breast masses or lumps. Breast self –examination, carried out once monthly, between the 7th and 10th day of the menstrual cycle, goes a long way in detecting breast cancer at the early stages of growth when there is low risk of spread, ensuring a better prognosis when treated (Schechter *et al.*, 1990). The aim of this study was to evaluate the knowledge and attitude of breast cancer self examination among female students in tertiary institutions in Nigeria

All women over the age of 20 should practice regular monthly self breast examinations. The importance of this cannot be over emphasized since an early cancer can be discovered by this method when mammography is normal. The examination should be done when the breasts are least tender, usually 7 days after the start of menstrual period. If a woman detects any changes or lumps, she should seek medical attention. Remember that 9 out of 10 women will not develop breast cancer and most breast changes are *not* cancerous.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in Bayelsa and Rivers State between March and August 2010 to assess knowledge, attitude and practice of breast cancer self examination among female students in tertiary institutions. Bayelsa and Rivers State have the largest crude oil and natural gas deposits in Nigeria. They are mainly rural dwellers due to its peculiar terrain; Bayelsa population is estimated to be about 1,998,349, while Rivers State is estimated to be 6,689,087.

The present study was based on data from five hundred and thirty four (534) female students with age ranging from 16 to 45 with a mean \pm standard deviation 30.5 ± 20.5 . Data collection was with the aid of questionnaires designed to obtain relevant knowledge, attitude and practice towards breast cancer. Questions on knowledge of study participants on risk factors, common symptoms, methods of early detection, Breast self examination (BSE). Most of the questions were designed to elicit "yes", "no" or "don't know" answers. Socio-demographic information relating to age, educational status, religion, and marital status were collected in the first section of the questionnaire. In the second part, respondents were asked specific questions to elicit their knowledge of the common symptoms and signs of breast cancer, etiological factors and diagnostic procedures. The third section examined participant's action and attitude towards practice of breast self examination (BSE).

Informed consent was granted by individual subjects. Data analysis was by the use of PAST version 2.01: Paleontology Statistical Software Package for Education and Data Analysis.

RESULTS

The ages of the respondents ranged from 16–45 years, 441 (83%), where from age group 16-25, 81 (15%) from age group 26- 35 and 12 (2%) from age group 36-45. Only 54 (10%) of the respondents were married, while 480 (90%) were single at the time of this research. Almost all the respondents were Christians (99.4%), there was no Muslim, while less than one percent (0.6) were from other religions. 357 (75%) of subjects reside in an urban area, 72 (15%) in suburban and 48 (10%) in rural area. Table 1

Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women

The female students in tertiary institutions showed good knowledge of breast cancer. A greater number of the respondents 477 (89%) agreed the breast cancer is most common in women, 42 (8%) disagreed and 12 (3%) did not know if breast cancer is the most common cancer in women or not.

Breast cancer occur more commonly in old people

On group of individuals in which breast cancer occur more commonly respondents had a poor knowledge as 285 (53%) said it is not common in old people, 168 (31%) agreed that it occur more in older people. While 81 (16%) had no idea.

Breast can be inherited

There was a poor knowledge on the etiology of breast cancer as only 207 (39%) were aware that breast cancer can be inherited. 195 (37%) of the female students believe that breast cancer can be caused by evil spirit, while 129 (27%) had no idea if it was caused by evil spirit or not.

Breast cancer usually present as a painless breast lump

Respondents had a very good knowledge of the signs and symptoms of breast cancer as 372 (72%) agreed that breast cancer usually present as a painless breast lump, 84 (16%), Disagreed while 57 (12%) were not aware of its signs and symptoms.

Breast cancer is curable when detected early

A large population of the respondents 441 (84%) said "Yes" while 48 (9%) said "No" and 39 (7%) said "I don't know" (Table 2)

Table 1:

Demographic characteristics of respondents.			
Demographic characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age group	16–25 years	441	83
	26–35 years	81	15
	36–45 years	12	2
Marital status	Married	54	10
	Single	480	90
Religion	Christian	531	99.4
	Muslim	0	0
	Others	3	0.6
Residence	Urban	357	75
	Suburban	72	15
	Rural	48	10

Table 2: Response of participants to selected questions on breast cancer

Knowledge	<i>f</i>	%
Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women		
Yes	477	89
No	42	8
I don't know	15	3
Breast cancer occur more commonly in old people		
Yes	168	31
No	285	53
I don't know	81	16
Breast can be inherited		
Yes	207	39
No	195	37
I don't know	129	27
Breast cancer is caused by evil spirits		
Yes	24	5
No	455	85
I don't know	54	10
Breast cancer usually present as a painless breast lump		
Yes	372	72
No	84	16
I don't know	57	12
Breast cancer is curable when detected early		
Yes	441	84
No	48	9
I don't know	39	7

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according to practice of breast self examination (BSE)

Practice of breast self examination	F	%
Breast self examination is useful in early diagnosis		
Yes	525	98.5
No	3	0.5
I don't know	6	1
Frequency of practice of breast self examination		
Once a month	255	49
Once in two months	39	7
Three to five times a year	39	7
Twice a year	15	3
Once a year	18	4
Not at all	159	30
*Source of knowledge of breast self examination		
From a doctor	213	37
Publications	153	27
Television	70	12
Churches/religious groups	18	3
Women organizations	33	6
Nigerian Cancer Society programs	84	15
Reasons for not practicing breast self examination		
I don't have breast problem	75	48
I don't think I should	9	6
I just don't feel like doing it	45	29
I don't think I will find anything	15	10
I leave it for doctors and nurses to do	9	6
Fear of having it	3	2

** The respondent could choose more than one response category. The percentages are based on total responses and not total number of the respondent*

Distribution of respondents according to practice of breast self examination (BSE)

The respondents performed best on the question if "breast self examination is useful in early diagnosis" as 525 (98.5%) said "Yes", 3 (0.5%) said "No" and 6 (1%) did not know. The performance was dashed when a total of 159(30%) had not practiced breast cancer self examination, 255 (49%) practice once in a month, 39(7%) practice once in two months and three to five times a year, 15(3%) practice twice a year and 18(4%)once a year.

Out of 159 (30%) that had not practiced breast cancer self examination, 75 (48%) said they don't have breast cancer as their reason, 9 (6%) said they don't think they should practice it, 45 (29%) said they don't just feel like doing it, 15 (10%) said they don't think they will find anything, 9 (6%) said they leave it for the doctors and nurses to check and 3 (2%) said they are afraid of practicing it.

Source of knowledge of breast self examination

Two hundred and thirteen (37%) of the respondents claimed to have heard about breast cancer self examination through a doctor, 153 (27%) from publications, 70 (12%) acknowledged Television, 18(3%) claimed their source was from churches/religious groups, while 33 (6%) of the respondents got their information from women organizations and 84(15%) from Nigerian cancer society programs. Table 3

DISCUSSION

The result reveals that Nigerian female students in tertiary institution [477 (89%)] have a good knowledge of breast cancer been the most common in women. This study agrees with an earlier study among women in Nigeria were 72.6% (Okobia *et al.*, 2006) and in Iran where 61% (Ali *et al.*, 2008) of the respondents agreed that breast cancer is the commonest in women. On the etiology of breast cancer there was poor knowledge as only 207 (39%) agreed that breast cancer can be inherited, while 195 (37%) disagreed that breast cancer can not be inherited and 129 (27%) claimed not to know if breast cancer can be inherited or not. This indicates that the etiology of breast cancer is not properly known among female students in tertiary schools in Nigeria. This findings is also in line with the research carried out in semi-urban area of Edo State Nigeria (Okobia *et al.*, 2006) where only 244(26%) of that population agreed that breast cancer be inherited. Though 455 (85%) agreed that breast cancer is not caused by evil spirit, 54 (10%) still believe it is coursed by evil spirit and 24 (5%) did not know if it causes it or not, this is totally not in conformity with the research carried out in the above mentioned location, where 400 (40%) of that population believed that evil spirits causes breast cancer and a lower population of 259 (25.9%) indicated that breast cancer results from an infection. These findings affirm the educational disparity between female students and semi-urban women dwellers.

There was a good knowledge of the sign / symptom of breast cancer as 372(72%) agreed that breast cancer usually presents as a painless lump. This is in line with the study carried out in Lagos among teachers (Oduanya, 2001) and a study from U.K indicated that 70% of women were well aware of 'painless lump' and able to identify these symptoms in their breast self examination (Grunfeld *et al.*, 2002) but contrary to the studies carried out in Ibadan 1.9% acknowledged a painless lump as an early warning sign (Oluwatosin and Oladepo, 2006). A large population of the respondents 441(84%) correctly noted that breast cancer is curable when detected early; this findings did not correspond with the findings in Benin where 41% agreed (Okobia *et al.*, 2006).

Breast Self Examination was known by almost all of the respondents to useful in early diagnosis, as 525(98.5%) said yes. This is findings agreed with the study carried out in Ilorin, where 95% heard about it (Kayode, 2005), the findings also agreed with findings reported from Enugu and Lagos both in Nigeria where 92% of the respondents were aware of the procedure (Nwagbo and Akpala, 1996; Odeyemi and Oyediran, 2002). The figure reported from a study in Port-Harcourt, Nigeria was less, where 89.4% of those studied had heard about it (Uche, 1998). Irrespective of the good knowledge in the usefulness of breast cancer self examination, less than average [255(49%)] of the respondents practice breast cancer self examination once in a month. This was higher (71.8%) in the study carried out in Ilorin, Nigeria (Kayode, 2005). It was interesting to observe that 159 (30%) had never practiced breast cancer self examination.

The highest proportion of the respondents obtained their information from a doctor 213 (37%), though poor, but has not been reported in any study as been the highest source for breast cancer self examination. 153 (27%) claimed they got the information from publication, Nigerian Cancer Society programs 85 (15%), television 70 (12%) the radio. Women organizations 33 (6%) and Churches/religious groups 18 (3%).

This study indicates doctors as the major source of information of breast cancer self examination. There was good of knowledge of breast cancer by the respondent but the practice of breast cancer self examination was below average which suggest that irrespective of the knowledge acquired, the practice of breast cancer self examination was still poor among female students in tertiary institutions.

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Received for Publication: 19/09/2010

Accepted for Publication: 18/10/2010

Correspondence Author

F.M. Onyije,

Department of Human Anatomy, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

E-mail: onyijefelix@yahoo.com